

西安财经学院 信息学院

编译原理 实验报告

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实验名称 正规式、自动机的相互转换
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一、实验目的

1. 理解正规式、NFA、DFA、DFA 最小化的基本原理；
2. 掌握正规式向 NFA 转换的算法；
3. 掌握 NFA 向 DFA 转换的算法；
4. 掌握 DFA 最小化的算法。

二、实验内容

1. 设计并实现正规式向 NFA 转换的算法；
2. 设计并实现 NFA 向 DFA 转换的算法；
3. 设计并实现 DFA 最小化的算法。

三、实验要求

1. 从下列实验内容中任选一个或几个算法实现；
 - (1) 设计并实现正规式向 NFA 转换的算法：输入为正规式，输出为一个 NFA。
 - (2) 设计并实现 NFA 向 DFA 转换的算法：输入为一个 NFA 五元组，输出一个与其等价的 DFA 五元组。
 - (3) 设计并实现 DFA 最小化的算法：输入为任意一个 DFA，输出此 DFA 等价的状态最少的 DFA。
2. 要求根据算法要求设计合理的数据结构；
3. 编程实现转换过程。

四、算法设计

4.1 自动机的数据结构与算法

4.1.1 自动机的数据结构

自动机由元组 (Σ, S, S_0, F, f) 组成, 其中

1. Σ 为字符的集合, 空串 $\epsilon \notin \Sigma$
2. S 为状态集合
3. $S_0 \in S$ 为初始态
4. $F \subset S$ 是终态的集合
5. $f: S \times (\Sigma \cup \{\epsilon\}) \rightarrow S$ 为状态转换函数, 在程序中可以使用哈希表 $\text{hash}(S_i, S_{j_k}) = C_{ij_k}$, $\forall c_{ij_k} \in C_{ij_k}$, 使得 $f(S_i, c_{ij_k}) = S_{j_k}$ 在 python 中, hash 函数由字典数 *dict* 据类型直接实现, 对于两个变量的哈希表, 可以用字典嵌套字典实现

4.1.2 自动机的算法

设正则表达式 s, t , 其对应 NFA 为 $N(s), N(t)$

对于表达式 $s|t$ 对于运算链接 (concatenation) $N(s)N(t)$, 对应的算法如算法 1

算法 1 concatenation 运算

$\text{concatenation}(N(s), N(t))$

- 1 **renameState**($N(t)$) \triangleright 修改 $N(t)$ 状态名, 防止歧义
 - 2 **merge**($N(s), N(t)$) \triangleright 将 $N(t)$ 的状态和转换函数复制给 $N(s)$
 - 3 $F_s \leftarrow F_t$ \triangleright $N(s)$ 的终态变为 $N(t)$ 的终态 F_t
 - 4 **free**($N(t)$) \triangleright 释放 $N(t)$ 的空间
 - 5 **return** $N(s)$
-

并运算 (**union**) $N(s)|N(t)$

算法 2 union 运算

```
union( $N(s), N(t)$ )
1  rename( $N(s)$ )
2  rename( $N(t)$ )
3  copy( $N(s), N(t)$ )
4  new  $S_0 \triangleright$  新初态
5  new  $S_t \triangleright$  新终态
6  addEdge( $S_0, S_0^{(s)}, \epsilon$ )  $\triangleright S_0^{(s)}$  为原  $N(s)$  的初态
7  addEdge( $S_0, S_0^{(t)}, \epsilon$ )  $\triangleright S_0^{(t)}$  为原  $N(t)$  的初态
8  for  $S_f \in F^{(s)} \cap F^{(t)}$ :
9      addEdge( $S_f, S_t, \epsilon$ )
10  $F \leftarrow \{S_t\} \triangleright$  新的终态集
11 free( $N(t)$ )
12 return  $N(s)$ 
```

对于 s^* 的形式，表示 s 匹配一次或多次，对自动机来说，无条件地进入终态，无条件返回初态，如算法 3

算法 3 star 运算

```
star( $N(t)$ )
1 for  $S_f \in F$ :
2     addEdge( $S_f, S_0, \epsilon$ )
3     addEdge( $S_0, S_f, \epsilon$ )
4 return  $N(t)$ 
```

4.2 正则表达式解析

正则表达式的结构可以由以下解析式组成

```
<regex> ::= <term> '|' <regex>
          | <term>

<term>  ::= { <factor> }

<factor> ::= <base> { '*' }
```

```
<base> ::= <char>
        | '\ ' <char>
        | '(' <regex> ')'
```

这些算法可以用递归实现，我们首先完成以下函数

1. peek() 查看模式串中下一个字符
2. eat(*c*) 检查下一个字符是否为 *c*，如果是，将模式串中去掉该元素，即返回第一个字符之后的元素
3. next() 返回下一个元素，并在模式串中去掉该元素

我们从最简单的部分开始，首先通过算法 4 检测 base, 处理转义符，括号和普通单个字母

算法 4 base 部分的解析

base()

- 1 **if** peek() = '(': ▷ 匹配括号
- 2 eat('(') ▷ 处理掉 '('
- 3 r ← regex() ▷ 这一部分为另一个正则表达式, 在算法 7 实现
- 4 eat(')')
- 5 **return** r ▷ 此时括号内的表达式的 NFA 是解析结果
- 6 **else if** peek() = '\': ▷ 处理转义符之后的字符
- 7 eat('\ ')
- 8 esc ← next() ▷ 获得转义符之后的一个字符
- 9 **return** basicConstruct(esc) ▷ 创建只含有 *esc* 的 NFA
- 10 **else** :
- 11 **return** basicConstruct(next()) ▷ 只有一种字母的情况

factor 部分由 base 和若干个 * 组成，我们对算法 4 的结果进行 star 运算 (算法 3) 具体过程如算法 5

算法 5 factor 部分的解析

factor()

- 1 base ← base() ▷ 从算法 4 中得到 * 之前部分的 NFA
 - 2 **while** parttern **and** peek() = '*': ▷ 处理所有 '*' 字符, 并进行相应运算
 - 3 eat('*')
 - 4 star(base) ▷ 对 base 进行 star 运算 (算法 3)
 - 5 **return** base
-

term 部分由若干个 factor 组成, 他们之间用 concatenation 运算链接 (算法 1) 具体实现如算法 6

算法 6 term 部分的解析

term()

- 1 term ← basicConstruct(ϵ) ▷ 只有空串转换的 NFA
 - 2 **while** pattern **and** peek() ≠ ')' **and** peek() ≠ '*': ▷ 下一个字符不能是需要运算符号
 - 3 f ← factor() ▷ 读取下一个 term (算法 5)
 - 4 term ← concatenation(term, f) ▷ 更新 term
 - 5 **return** term
-

最终, 我们可以将一个正则表达式分解为 term 或者 term '|' regex 的形式我们对相应 NFA union 运算 (算法 2) 然后得到最终的 NFA 具体细节见算法 7

算法 7 regex 部分的解析

regex()

- 1 term ← term() ▷ 第一部分为 term 部分
 - 2 **if** pattern **and** peek() = '|':
 - 3 regex ← regex() ▷ 下一部分是另一个正则表达式, 用自身解析
 - 4 **else** :
 - 5 **return** term
-

五、实验步骤与结果

5.1 代码测试自动机的基本构造

构造自动机类的数据类型和相关方法，并检查状态转换是否正确，运行

```
test = Automata('ab')
test.set_start_state(1)
test.add_final_states(2)
test.add_final_states(2)
test.add_transition(1,2,set(['a', 'b']))
test.add_transition(1,3,set('b'))
test.draw('../docs/figures/test_automata.pdf')
```

其中打印显示数据类型如下

```
{1: {2: {'a', 'b'}, 3: {'b'}}}
states: {1, 2, 3}
start state: 1
final state: {2}
transitions:
1->2 on 'a'
1->2 on 'b'
1->3 on 'b'
```

绘图结果如图 1

图 1 测试一个自动机的数据结构

图 1 蓝色点代表终态，红色代表初态，其他状态为绿色

5.2 测试自动机的方法和运算

接下来测试自动机的运算，对于图 2a 中的自动机 N_1 和图 2b 中的自动机 N_2

图 2 简单的自动机

根据算法 3 测试 $\text{star}(N(s))$ 结果如

图 3 star 运算测试结果

接下来完成算法 2 并测试 $N(s), N(t)$ 如图 4

图 4 union 运算测试

最后根据算法 1 完成 concatenation 运算代码并绘图，得

图 5 concatenation($N(s), N(t)$) 的结果

5.3 测试正则表达式解析

根据 算法 (4) ~ (7) 完成正则表达式解析算法我们测试正则表达式 $a|b$ 得到图 6

图 6 正则表达式 $a|b$ 生成的 NFA

图 6 中 $6 \rightarrow 7, 8 \rightarrow 11$ 展示了状态转换的逻辑，但是算法中引入大量空串，使生成 NFA 变得复杂，对于像 $(a|b)^*ab$ 这样复杂的表达式 () 视觉上很难识别转换关系需要进一步化简。

图 7 比较复杂的表达式 $(a|b)^*ab$

六、实验总结

这部分实验是一组算法，非常锻炼逻辑能力和设计能力，对数据类型的封装可以应用许多面向对象技术，如实现运算时，可以使用一个对象的方法更新，也可以使用静态方法，基本的自动机类型可以由工厂模式的类方法构造，这一些对以后的程序设计很有帮助。

算法方面，文字的分析很好的展现了递归的简单优雅，利用递归可以快速构造代码，且符合思考的逻辑，但是如果进一步想优化算法，需要利用栈来做进一步分析。

这一类算法的调试，分析都是从小的部分自顶而上构造，自顶而下的思考分析，锻炼了逻辑思维。

对于网上的算法，需要自己的理解分析对于网上的代码需要改造为自己理解的形式，直接不假思索的复制，沉迷于低质量的信息，在我的实验过程中看到了一些经典的讲解^[2]和一些完整的实现^[3]这一些都是参考学习的优质资源，比许多明显是别的学生作业的资源优质许多，这些可以对照我们学过的理论^[1]对编译系统有更深入的了解，进而熟悉一套解析的逻辑，增强自己的能力

附录 A 依赖的安装

本文代码的 `Atutomata.draw()` 方法依赖

```
network2tikz
```

可以通过以下命令在清华镜像网站安装全部

```
pip install -i http://mirrors.aliyun.com/pypi/simple \  
--trusted-host mirrors.aliyun.com/pypi/simple/ \  
-r requirements.txt
```

如果在程序中不使用画图功能，可以忽略安装

附录 B 自动机的相关方法与测试源代码

```
"""  
filename src/Automata.py  
reference https://github.com/sdht0/automata-from-regex/blob/master/AutomataTheory.py  
"""  
from __future__ import annotations # type hint within a class  
from typing import *  
# see https://stackoverflow.com/questions/41135033/type-hinting-within-a-class  
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt  
import networkx as nx
```

```

import matplotlib as mpl
plt.rcParams.update({
    "text.usetex": True,
    "font.family": "sans-serif",
    "font.sans-serif": ["Helvetica"]})
# for Palatino and other serif fonts use:
plt.rcParams.update({
    "text.usetex": True,
    "font.family": "serif",
    "font.serif": ["Palatino"],
})

class Automata:
    """
    class to represent a automata

    :param input_alphabet: a set of input symbols
    :type input_alphabet: set,optional

    :ivar empty_string: empty string, denoted by :math:`\epsilon`
    :ivar self.states: a finite states of S
    :ivar self.transitions: 11
    :ivar self.input_alphabet: a set of input symbols
    :ivar self.final_states: the set of final state
    :ivar self.transitions: the transitions functions,
        `translations[f][t] = d` where f is from state,t in to state,
        d is the dict of states where d[state] = set of input symbols
    """
    empty_string = set([r'\epsilon'])

    def __init__(self, input_alphabet: set):
        self.states = set() # a finite states of S
        self.input_alphabet = input_alphabet # a set of input symbols
        self.start_state = None
        self.final_states = set()
        self.transitions = dict()

    # @staticmethod
    # def empty_string() -> str:
    #     r"""get the symbol of empty_string symbol :math:`\epsilon`

    #     :return: r'\epsilon'
    #     :rtype: str
    #     """
    #     return r'\epsilon'

```

```

def set_start_state(self, state: int):
    """set the start state

    :param state: the label of start state
    :type state: int
    """
    self.start_state = state
    self.states.add(state)

def add_final_states(self, *states):
    """add the final states

    :param states: the list of states
    """
    for state in states:
        self.final_states.add(state)

def add_transition(self, from_state: int, to_state: int, input_symbols: set):
    """add the transition to transfer functions
    (`self.transitions` in the program)

    :param from_state: the begin state
    :type from_state: int
    :param to_state: the next state
    :type to_state: int
    :param input_symbols: the transfer symbols to the next states
    :type input_symbols: set
    """

    self.states.add(from_state)
    self.states.add(to_state)
    if from_state in self.transitions:
        if to_state in self.transitions[from_state]:
            self.transitions[from_state][to_state].update(input_symbols)
        else:
            self.transitions[from_state][to_state] = input_symbols
    else:
        self.transitions[from_state] = {to_state: input_symbols}

def add_transition_from_dict(self, translations: Dict[int, Dict[int, set]]):
    """
    :param translations: translations[f][t] = d where f is from state,t in to state,
                        d is the dict of states where d[state] = set of input symbols
    :type translations: dict
    """
    for from_state, to_states in translations.items():
        for to_state, input_symbols in to_states.items():

```

```

        self.add_transition(from_state, to_state, input_symbols)

def __repr__(self):
    """
    display the information of the automata
    """
    trans = ""
    for from_state, to_states in self.transitions.items():
        for to_state, symbols in to_states.items():
            for char in symbols:
                trans += f"\t{from_state}->{to_state} on '{char}'\n"
            trans += '\n'

    return f"states:\t{self.states}\n" \
           f"start state:\t{self.start_state}\n" \
           f"final state:\t{self.final_states}\n" \
           f"transitions:\n{trans}"

def rename(self, offset: int) -> None:
    """change the state name to prevent the conflict

    :param offset: offset the number
    :type offset: int
    """
    self.states = set(i+offset for i in self.states)
    self.start_state += offset
    self.final_states = set(i+offset for i in self.final_states)

    # change the transition
    new_transitions = dict()
    for from_state, to_states in self.transitions.items():
        new_transitions[from_state+offset] = dict()
        for to_state in to_states.keys():
            new_transitions[from_state+offset][to_state+offset] = \
                self.transitions[from_state][to_state]

    self.transitions = new_transitions

def draw(self, save='temp.pdf', seed:int=None) -> None:
    """
    draw the graph

    :param save: save the save path (`reference <https://stackoverflow.com/a/20382152>`)
    :type save: str
    :param seed: the node location random seed
    :type seed: int

```

```
if you haven't installed network2tikz,  
you need install it by
```

```
.. code-block:: bash
```

```
    pip install -U network2tikz
```

```
"""  
from network2tikz import plot  
nodes = list(self.states)  
node_colors = [  
    'green!20' if node not in self.final_states else 'blue!20' for node in self.states]  
node_colors[nodes.index(self.start_state)] = "red!20"  
edges = []  
edge_labels = []  
for from_state, to_states in self.transitions.items():  
    for to_state, symbols in to_states.items():  
        edges.append((from_state, to_state))  
        labels = []  
        for symbol in symbols:  
            labels.append(symbol)  
        edge_labels.append("| ".join(labels))  
  
plot((nodes, edges), save,  
     # layout="spring_layout",  
     seed=seed,  
     canvas=(10,10),  
     node_label_as_id=True,  
     node_color=node_colors,  
     edge_label=edge_labels,  
     edge_math_mode=True, edge_directed=True, edge_curved=0.2,  
     edge_label_position='left')  
  
@classmethod  
def empty_construct(cls):  
    """construct a empty construct of a automata  
  
    :return: the empty automata  
    :rtype: Automata  
    """  
    return cls.basic_construct(set([r'\epsilon']))  
  
@classmethod  
def basic_construct(cls, symbol: set):  
    """construct NFA with a single symbol  
  
    :param symbol: the symbol
```

```

:type symbol: str
:return: a NFA
:rtype: Automata
"""
basic = Automata(symbol)
basic.set_start_state(1)
basic.add_final_states(2)
basic.add_transition(1, 2, set(symbol))
return basic

@staticmethod
def star_operation(nfa):
    """process the star operation

    .. note::

        the nfa is changed after call the method

    :param nfa: the previous NFA
    :type nfa: Automata
    :return: the new NFA after processing star operation
        that means add two string in the begin state and end state
    :rtype: Automata
    """
    for final_state in nfa.final_states:
        nfa.add_transition(nfa.start_state, final_state,
                           set([r"\epsilon"]))
        nfa.add_transition(final_state, nfa.start_state,
                           set([r"\epsilon"]))

    return nfa

@staticmethod
def concatenation(basic: Automata, addition: Automata) -> Automata:
    """union two Automata

    :param basic: this Automata will be changed after union
    :type basic: Automata
    :param addition: This Automata will be deleted after union
    :type addition: Automata
    :return: [description]
    :rtype: Automata
    """
    # to manage the state name conflict
    offset = max(basic.states)
    addition.rename(offset)

```

```

basic.add_transition_from_dict(addition.transitions)
for pre_final in basic.final_states:
    basic.add_transition(pre_final, addition.start_state,
                        Automata.empty_string)

basic.final_states = addition.final_states
del addition
return basic

@staticmethod
def union(basic: Automata, parallel: Automata) -> Automata:
    """handle the regex s|t by union these NFA

    :param basic: the NFA will change after union
    :type basic: Automata
    :param parallel: the NFA will be deleted after union
    :type parallel: Automata
    :return: The new NFA based on `basic`
    :rtype: Automata
    """
    # rename the two graph
    basic.rename(offset=1)
    offset = max(basic.states)
    parallel.rename(offset)

    # update edges
    basic.add_transition_from_dict(parallel.transitions)

    # update the start
    new_start_state = min(basic.states) - 1
    basic.add_transition(new_start_state,
                        basic.start_state, Automata.empty_string)
    basic.add_transition(new_start_state, parallel.start_state,
                        Automata.empty_string)
    basic.set_start_state(new_start_state)

    # handle the final states
    new_final_state = max(parallel.states)+1
    pre_finals = basic.final_states.union(parallel.final_states)
    for pre_final in pre_finals:
        basic.add_transition(
            pre_final, new_final_state, Automata.empty_string)
    basic.final_states = set([new_final_state])

    del parallel
    return basic

```

```

if __name__ == "__main__":
    def figure_path(s):
        return f"../reports/regex_parser/figures/{s}.pdf"

    # basic test
    test = Automata(set('ab'))
    test.set_start_state(1)
    test.add_final_states(2)
    test.add_final_states(2)
    test.add_transition(1, 2, set(['a', 'b']))
    test.add_transition(1, 1, set('b'))
    print(test.transitions)
    print(test)
    test.draw('../reports/regex_parser/figures/test_automata.pdf',seed=2) # 2
    """ output
    {1: {2: {'a', 'b'}, 1: {'b'}}}
    states: {1, 2}
    start state: 1
    final state: {2}
    transitions:
        1->2 on 'a'
        1->2 on 'b'
        1->1 on 'b'
    """
    print(test.transitions)
    test.rename(3)
    print(test)
    """output
    {1: {2: {'a', 'b'}, 1: {'b'}}}
    states: {4, 5}
    start state: 4
    final state: {5}
    transitions:
        4->5 on 'a'
        4->5 on 'b'
        4->4 on 'b'
    """

    # test basic construct
    test1 = Automata.basic_construct(set(['a']))
    test1.draw(save="../reports/regex_parser/figures/basic_a.pdf",seed=1)
    print(test1)
    """
    states: {1, 2}
    start state: 1
    final state: {2}

```

```

transitions:
    1->2 on 'a'
"""

# test star operation
test1 = Automata.star_operation(test1)
print(test1)
test1.draw('../reports/regex_parser/figures/test_star.pdf',seed=1)
r"""output
    states: {1, 2}
    start state: 1
    final state: {2}
    transitions:
        1->2 on '\epsilon'
        1->2 on 'a'

        2->1 on '\epsilon'
"""

# test link operation
test1 = Automata.basic_construct(set(['a']))
test2 = Automata.basic_construct(set(['b']))
test2.draw(figure_path('basic_b'),seed=1)
print(Automata.concatenation(test1, test2))
test1.draw(save=figure_path('test_concatenation'),seed=2) # 2
r"""output
    states: {1, 2}
    start state: 1
    final state: {2}
    transitions:
        1->2 on 'a'
        1->2 on '\epsilon'

        2->1 on '\epsilon'
"""

# test parallel union
test1 = Automata.basic_construct(set(['a']))
test2 = Automata.basic_construct(set(['b']))
test3 = Automata.union(test1, test2)
test3.draw(save=figure_path('test_union'),seed=79744993) # 1111
# import random
# for i in range(50):
#     s = int(random.random() * 100000000)
#     test3.draw(f'/tmp/{s}.pdf',seed=s)
print(test3)
r"""output

```

```
states: {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6}
start state: 1
final state: {6}
transitions:
    2->3 on 'a'

    4->5 on 'b'

    1->2 on '\epsilon'
    1->4 on '\epsilon'

    3->6 on '\epsilon'

    5->6 on '\epsilon'
"""
```

附录 C 正则表达式的解析

```
from Automata import Automata

class RegexParser:
    """
    store and parse a pattern

    .. code-block:: text

    <regex> ::= <term> '|' <regex>
              | <term>

    <term> ::= { <factor> }

    <factor> ::= <base> { '*' }

    <base> ::= <char>
              | '\\' <char>
              | '(' <regex> ')'

    :param pattern: the pattern to match the string
    :type pattern: str

    :ivar self.pattern: the pattern
    :ivar self.NFA: the NFA machine
    """
```

```

# alphabet = set([chr(i) for i in range(65, 91)])\
#   .union([chr(i) for i in range(97, 123)])\
#   .union([chr(i) for i in range(48, 58)])

def __init__(self, pattern: str):
    """store and parse a pattern

    :param pattern: the pattern to match the string
    :type pattern: str
    """
    self.pattern = pattern
    # self.NFA = self.build_NFA()

# def build_NFA(self):
#     """build a NFA from pattern create :class:`Automata.Automata`

#     :return: the NFA of the current pattern

#     :rtype: Automata.Automata
#     """
#     language = set()
#     self.buffer = []
#     self.automata = []
#     previous = r'\epsilon'
#     for char in self.pattern:
#         if char in self.alphabet:
#             pass
#             # TODO
#     return None

def peek(self) -> str:
    """returns the next item of input without consuming it;

    :return: the next character
    :rtype: str
    """
    return self.pattern[0]

def eat(self, item:str) -> None:
    """eat(item) consumes the next item of input, failing if not equal to item.

    :param item: the next item
    :type item: str
    :raises RuntimeError: get the wrong letter.
    """

```

```

if(self.peek() == item):
    self.pattern = self.pattern[1:]
else:
    raise RuntimeError(f"expect: {item}; got {self.peek()}")

def next(self) -> str:
    """returns the next item of input and consumes it;

    :return: the next character
    :rtype: str
    """
    c = self.peek()
    self.eat(c)
    return c

def parse_base_part(self) -> Automata:
    """check the cases encountered

    .. code-block:: text

        <base> ::= <char>
                | '\\\' <char>
                | '(' <regex> ')

    :return: Automata of this part
    :rtype: Automata
    """
    if self.peek() == '(':
        self.eat('(')
        r = self.parse_regex()
        self.eat(')')
        return r

    elif self.peek() == '\\':
        self.eat('\\')
        esc = self.next()
        return Automata.basic_construct(esc)
    else:
        return Automata.basic_construct(self.next())

def parse_factor_part(self) -> Automata:
    base = self.parse_base_part()

    while(self.pattern and self.peek() == '*'):
        self.eat('*')
        base = Automata.star_operation(base)

```

```

return base

def parse_term_part(self) -> Automata:
    """check that it has not reached the boundary of a term or the end of the input:

    .. code-block:: text

        <term> ::= { <factor> }

    :return: the NFA of this part
    :rtype: Automata
    """
    factor = Automata.empty_construct()
    while(self.pattern and self.peek() != ') and self.peek() != '|'):
        next_factor = self.parse_factor_part()
        factor = Automata.concatenation(factor, next_factor)

    return factor

def parse_regex(self) -> Automata:
    """For regex() method, we know that we must parse at least one term,
    and whether we parse another

    .. code-block::text

        <regex> ::= <term> '|' <regex>
                | <term>

    :return: the NFA
    :rtype: Automata
    """
    term = self.parse_term_part()
    if(self.pattern and self.peek() == '|'):
        self.eat('|')
        regex = self.parse_regex()
        return Automata.union(term, regex)
    else:
        return term

if __name__ == "__main__":
    def figure_path(s):
        return f"./reports/regex_parser/figures/{s}.pdf"

    # test the cases of the only letter
    test1 = RegexParser("a")

```

```

print(test1.parse_base_part())
"""output
  states: {1, 2}
  start state: 1
  final state: {2}
  transitions:
    1->2 on 'a'
"""

# test the escape symbol
test2 = RegexParser("\\*")
print(test2.parse_base_part())
"""output
  states: {1, 2}
  start state: 1
  final state: {2}
  transitions:
    1->2 on '*'
"""

# test parse factor part
test3 = RegexParser('a*')
print(test3.parse_factor_part())
r"""output
  states: {1, 2}
  start state: 1
  final state: {2}
  transitions:
    1->2 on '\epsilon'
    1->2 on 'a'

    2->1 on '\epsilon'
"""

test4 = RegexParser('ab')
print(test4.parse_term_part())
r"""output
  states: {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6}
  start state: 1
  final state: {6}
  transitions:
    1->2 on '\epsilon'

    3->4 on 'a'

    2->3 on '\epsilon'
"""

```

5->6 on 'b'

4->5 on '\epsilon'

"""

```
nfa1 = RegexParser('(a|b)').parse_regex()
print(nfa1)
# # which is best
# import random
# import os
# import time
# l = []
# for i in range(100):
#     s = int(random.random() * 100000000)
#     nfa1.draw(f'/tmp/ab/{s}.pdf',seed=s)
#     l.append(s)
# time.sleep(10)
# for s in l:
#     os.system(f"pdftoppm /tmp/ab/{s}.pdf /tmp/ab/{s} -png")
nfa1.draw(save=figure_path("a|b"),seed=79870681)

# test a complex
nfa2 = RegexParser('(a|b)*ab').parse_regex()
nfa2.draw(save=figure_path('complex'),seed=53138909)
```